

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8053928>

Abstract. The article explores the theoretical approaches of various researchers related to the organization and development of small industrial zones. By comparing the studied theoretical approaches and the process of establishing small industrial zones in Uzbekistan, identified the directions for the development of national industries in the future.

Key words: industrial parks, eco-industrial park, resident of a small industrial area, NPV, PI, influencing factors, cooperation, infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

Today, special economic zones that are developing on a global scale, in particular, small industrial zones, have their own history of formation and development. Special economic zones of this form make it possible to develop steadily in the regions using the existing relative advantages of industries.

The formation and development of small industrial zones plays an important role in the development of the existing economic resource potential in the territory, coupled with the results of infrastructure and research institutes. Taking into account the above circumstances, the research work studied the history of the development of small industrial zones until today, as well as the theoretical aspects of research on the assessment of the effectiveness of the system in this form.

METHODOLOGY

In the theoretical study of the formation, development of small industrial zones and their SMA-dependence, it is possible to obtain the expected results by monographic research of the research results of researchers, as well as comparing the approaches of different researchers.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The history of the development of Industrial parks began in 1896 with the establishment of Trafford Park, the first in Manchester, England, and it was considered a planned engineering transport communications industrial area [1].

In 1992-93, the concept of Eco-industrial Parks appeared in the United States. It is a merger of manufacturing and service companies that aim to achieve co-production and environmental efficiency.

Currently, eco-industrial parks are common in Canada, India, Indonesia, China, the United States and Japan. In total, more than 20,000 industrial parks are currently operating in more than 90 States.

Development of industrial parks in the Russian Federation 2005

On July 22, the Law No. 116-F3 „On separate zones in the Russian Federation“ began with the adoption. But the law does not define industrial park.

The concept of Industrial Park has been described in many works [2, 3, 4]. Not to mention these definitions, let's dwell on the specific main features of industrial park:

- availability of decision on the construction of industrial Park by local authorities;
- availability of land area, the owner of the land can be a public or private investor;
- availability of engineering infrastructure (power supply, sewage, gas and water supply, telephone communications and communications);
- transport infrastructure (presence or proximity of iron and highway, car accommodation, gas station);
- availability of management company;
- financial infrastructure (close proximity of banking, credit organizations);
- social infrastructure (shop, medical points, catering facilities, recreation area).

In addition to these, the presence of a ready-made office, laboratory, warehouses, a residential complex for zone workers in the structure of the infrastructure of industrial park is considered normal.

benefits: tax benefits, material support of investors by the state, cooperative financing of the construction of the most important engineering infrastructure facilities, subsidizing interest rates;

unified concept of development of its territory, taking into account the specialization of industrial Park, location plan of its facilities to be built on the territory of the Park, marketing strategy;

marketability;

the possibility of obtaining natural and labor resources.

One of the requirements for Industrial park is the integrated environmental impact of closely spaced Productions and the possibility of building them side by side. One of the main features of the Industrial park is that they can be erected on land plots owned by the state, municipal authorities and legal entities. Whether it is an industrial park or an industrial zone in the Russian Federation, they are managed by a management company.

The management company is selected on a concourse basis. The management company has a large number of types of services, which include: preparation of documents related to planning to adapt the land area to the industrial park; planning and construction of infrastructure facilities; Organization of construction and use of Park infrastructure facilities; Geological Survey of the territory; rental or sale of land areas, buildings and infrastructure facilities; finding and attracting financial funds to; providing services to engineering networks, complex of economic Park facilities and residents; helping residents to place enterprises in the Park area, providing the necessary Labor, energy, natural and other resources; offering outsourcing service in the implementation of business activities of residents in accounting, financial, legal, economic issues, logistics and Customs; guarding the industrial zone, ensuring the cleanliness of the territory, establishing fire.

Industrial parks, according to the International Classification by the type of services provided to residents, are divided into two types [2, 4]:

Greenfield – industrial Park offers of land for the construction of production buildings and facilities and provides on-demand construction services. On the dominant side, the entrepreneur builds production facilities at his discretion. The disadvantage: starting construction from scratch costs a lot of money, and construction can stretch in time.

Brownfield – industrial park has production facilities, are pre-built and are ready for sale to residents or for rental. On the dominant side ready-made production buildings, the disadvantage: to spend additional capital on demolition and reconstruction of buildings that are not suitable for production.

The resident of Industrial park is a legal entity engaged in production activities on the territory of industrial Park on the basis of a contract with a management company. In our opinion, the clear designation of residents of small industrial zones is one of the important organizational issues.

Potential residents of small industrial areas can be defined as follows¹:

1. Small business and business entities.
2. Powers or branches of Republican or foreign production and service companies.
3. Representative offices of supplier companies (at the same time foreign).
4. Banking, customs, marketing, insurance and Exchange branches.

The introduction of paragraphs 2-4 expands the economic ties of small industrial zones, the possibilities of working in cooperation.

Industrial parks also have certain requirements for placing residents on a competitive basis. In particular, the following requirements are imposed on the value of indicators of financial, budgetary and economic efficiency:

- that the net quoted value is positive, i.e. $(NPV > 0)$;
- internal rate of return $(IRR > 0.1)$;
- coverage period-should be less than 7 years;
- profitability index (PI) above 1.

These indicators are calculated on each investment project that will be located in industrial park. We think that the application of these demand indicators in accordance with the projects of investment, which will be placed in small industrial zones under the conditions of Uzbekistan, will be appropriate in our opinion.

In general, in industrialized countries, the forms of territorial organization of industry are very well developed, and a large, rich experience has been accumulated in this area. The use of this experience makes it possible to increase the construction and development of small industrial zones in Uzbekistan to a higher level, both theoretical and practical. The promotion and activation of the creation of small industrial zones leads to a further increase in the volume of industrial production, an increase in competitive product production by accelerating the use of advanced technologies and innovations, the creation of new jobs. Small industrial zones Save on the cost of entrepreneurs, as a result of which the opportunities for the development of small industrial zones in the districts of the Republic with a low level of industry expand. In turn, it sets the stage for districts and territories to become industrialized areas.

The conditions created in small industrial areas will activate the business environment in the area while increasing their investment appeal. The development of small industrial zones ensures its further development by having a multiplicative effect on the economy of the territory.

Currently, one of the effective ways to develop small business and support it by the state is small industrial zones. Small industrial zones provide great opportunities for the

¹ Developed by author.

development of territories. In particular, it accelerates industrial production, increases the attractiveness of the regions for entrepreneurship investiture, provides a wide range of opportunities for attracting new investments and new technologies, stimulating entrepreneurial activity and their development, leads to the creation of jobs for the population and the production of new competitive products.

In the areas allocated for small industrial zones, there is a certain level of production infrastructure, that is, facilities with land area, water, gas, electroenergy and with an exit to highways, which are lacking, will be built at the expense of state funds. According to research carried out in the Russian Federation, while the Park is equipped with infrastructure, enterprises save up to 20 percent of the costs on infrastructure facilities. This leads to a sharp reduction in the initial costs that entrepreneurs spend on establishing their own business and accelerates the start-up of the business. The areas allocated for small industrial zones are rented to business entities at a minimum rate, for a long period without additional coefficients.

The placement of business entities in small industrial zones is carried out on a competitive basis. This approach gives small industrial zones the opportunity to attract entrepreneurs who are a competitive and exportable producer of products, that is, those who establish development based on modern techniques and technologies, and increases the competitiveness of small industrial zones.

Factors affecting the effectiveness of small industrial zones can be attributed to:

- the establishment of structures that provide general services to small business entities in small industrial zones will bring additional effect. For example: single warehouse service, transportation service, equipment and technology repair service, Supply Service, Guard service, etc.

- the establishment of cooperation between business entities in small industrial zones also leads to the effect of synergy, on the other hand, the opportunity to implement large projects that not every business entity can implement. For example, issues such as the purchase of expensive new equipment or technology, export support, the establishment of additional development cexs, the expansion of logistics services will have a good effect on cooperation. The above will lead to a reduction in the production costs of small industrial zones and an increase in the competitiveness of products.

The issues of organizing the construction of small industrial zones require the implementation of work related to the preparation of the zones themselves for the placement of production entities. It is necessary to align the fields, build engineering and communication elements, build a road that provides access to the central highway, wrap around the zone, determine how many small business entities can be placed in the zone, identify and place objects of service for business entities, how much space should be allocated for each business entity, place the types of production side by side, It is important to assess their economic efficiency when justifying the construction of small industrial zones.

Here, first of all, we think that it is necessary to focus on assessing the effectiveness of projects of business entities that will be placed in the zone area. At the next stage, the preparation of the zone area, in which the elements of engineering and communication, the assessment of the total economic efficiency of the zone, having reached the costs spent on the construction of service facilities, is an important indicator in the economic justification of the zone's activities. In addition, the assessment of the social efficiency of small industrial zones

and its integral impact on the environment are also important indicators in justifying the establishment of zones. Here it is envisaged to create new jobs, provide the population with income, achieve a minimum level of negative impact of small industrial zones on the environment.

The assessment of the economic efficiency of small industrial zones can be carried out according to the following stages:

preparation of the territory, determination of the costs for the creation of production infrastructure facilities, that is, the costs of water, gas, electricity supply and the creation of highways;

determine the effectiveness of each business entity project according to its business plan;

calculation of income from the sale of products produced in small industrial zones, profit and profit from the provision of services;

calculation of costs associated with the organization of structures that provide common services to small business entities in the zones;

assessment of the overall effectiveness of small industrial zones.

Assessment of the overall economic efficiency of the zone, having reached the costs spent on the construction of Service objects, is an important indicator in the economic justification of the zone's activities.

The organization of technoparks is one of the important directions when introducing the latest science and technology achievements into production in small industrial zones, establishing the production of high-science capacity and innovative products. The concept of "Technopark" is described differently in sources, but the definition given by the scientific Parks Association of England has been accepted by many [5, 6].

A Technopark is an organization that owns land and real estate, and it:

1. It has a formal working relationship with higher and educational institutions.
2. Its main task is to support education and ensure the development of high-tech companies and enterprises with high knowledge.
3. Acts as a management, actively participates in the process of granting technopark residents, technology transfer and business knowledge.

The technopark is an area with a high level of construction and conditions, in which the purpose of developing scientific research works and new technologies and their commercialization is set by placing companies, scientific research institutes and laboratories. Some authors comment on the industrial Technopark, equating it to the industrial zone.

According to the Technopark concept, it defines the issue of developing new technologies and their introduction into production, which requires that there be an element of scientific research on the territory of the Technopark.

Technopark is a subject of scientific and innovative infrastructure and creates the necessary conditions for the development of scientific companies producing products in the scientific and technical field, it has an equipped eksperemental base, social infrastructure and a highly qualified personnel structure.

In general, the differences between industrial Park, Technopark and small industrial zones are shown in Table 1. Small industrial zones differ from economic parks as well as technoparks in terms of land area and its composition, in the conduct of scientific research, source of funding, residents, tax and Customs benefits.

Table 1**Differences of Industrial Park, Technopark and small industrial zones²**

Criteriaes	Industrial Park	Technopark	Small industrial areas
Relationship with HEI	May be	Must be	None
Scientific research is carried out	Don't carried out	Carried out	Don't carried out
Economic geographical position	Close to major transportation route and sales market	Close to a research center or HEI	Not necessarily
Land area	The state, municipality, can swell in a place on land that is privately owned. In most cases around 100 hectares	Not required by minimum area, can be located in any building	The land area of state property can be less than or more than 10 hectares
Availability of knowledge capacity production	Not necessarily	Main function	Not necessarily
Privileged economic conditions	Tax relief, transportation and land tax privilege on. Is exempt from property taxes, the profit tax rate is reduced	There is a tax deduction: the property is exempt from the so League, the profit tax rate is reduced	Tax credit; customs privilege; credit privilege; rental privilege
Main residents	Enterprises of any type (Small, Medium, Large)	Small science capacity enterprises	Small businesses, microfirms
Construction of infrastructure	At the expense of public funds, private investors, public-private sector partnership	At the expense of public funds or a private investor	At the expense of the state budget
Legal basis	Decision of the local government	Decision of the local government	Presidential decision
Management	Management company	Head of the enterprise	Directorate or unified General Directorate

CONCLUSIONS² Developed by author.

While technoparks provide opportunities for technology development, implementation and commercialization, small industrial zones provide residents with infrastructure to provide them with the conditions to engage in manufacturing activities. The common sides of the Industrial Park, tax Park and small industrial zones are the presence and establishment of tax incentives in them. It can be said from the above that we can study small industrial zones as an independent economic category.

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